

Nigeria and South Africa Trade Relations: Issues and Challenges (2006 - 2023)

Japhet Audu, BEM

Centre for the Study of Leadership and Complex Military Operations,
Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna
bemaudu123@gmail.com; bemaudu@nda.edu.ng; +2348036325883

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Abu Ndah ALI

Department of History and War Studies, Nigerian Defence Academy, Kaduna
ndahabuali@yahoo.com; abundahali@gmail.com; +27766220741; +2348037021092

Abstract

Nigeria and South Africa, Africa's two largest economies, have long maintained a robust trade relationship. Although much research has been devoted to their economic exchanges, less attention has been paid to the challenges within their trade relations. The gap in current knowledge means that persistent economic challenges faced by both countries go unaddressed. Nigeria's over reliance on oil makes its economy vulnerable to global price changes and limits growth in other sectors like agriculture and manufacturing. South Africa, in contrast, boasts a more diversified but slow-growing economy plagued by high unemployment, energy issues, and socio-economic inequality. These differences are mirrored in the balance of trade and broader bilateral engagement. Despite a trade surplus with South Africa, Nigeria's intra-African trade accounts for only 10% of its exports. Major barriers to enhanced trade include inadequate infrastructure, difficult customs procedures and red tape, limited access to finance, and insufficient investment in human capital. Addressing these barriers, especially the non-tariff barriers, standards, conformity assessments, and simplified customs procedures are essential for both nations to unlock the full potential of their economic partnership and achieve sustainable transformation.

Keywords: African trade relations, Bilateral trade, Intra-African trade Nigeria, South Africa

Word count: 182

Introduction

Ancient civilizations established international trade as a result of the economic and cultural exchanges made possible by trade routes such as the Silk Road (Robinson, 2022). Before being disrupted by European colonization, early trade networks in Africa, such as the trans-Saharan and Indian Ocean routes, prospered. Trade relations were impacted by the new borders that colonialism imposed. African countries attempted to restore their economic independence after gaining it. The trade relationship between Nigeria and South Africa dates to the early post-

apartheid era, when South Africa began to reintegrate itself into the global economy (Tella, 2018; Mordi, Adewumi & Oyedokun, 2021; Adebajo, 2023). Nigeria, with its vast oil resources and growing consumer market, presented lucrative opportunities for South African businesses. Conversely, South Africa's diversified economy and advanced infrastructure attracted Nigerian investments and trade (Tella, 2018; Taku, 2017).

In order to support Africa's wider economic integration and development, South Africa and Nigeria, two strong economic actors in the continent, have deepened their bilateral ties through trade agreements, especially in industries like manufacturing, technology, and energy (Tella, 2018; Oyedokun, Mansur, & Awotomilusi 2019; Adebajo, 2023). Today, the economies of Nigeria and South Africa are still dominated by mineral resources such as gold, platinum, and oil. Both countries account for over 60% of the economies of Southern and West Africa respectively (Taku, 2017). With more than 220 million people, Nigeria is Africa's largest market in terms of population (World Population Review, 2024), Nigeria offers various trade and investment opportunities for countries like South Africa which is continually expanding its presence beyond Southern Africa (Tella, 2018; Adebajo, 2023). The country's economic growth has averaged 2% annually from 2017 to 2023, falling short of the government's target of 7% per annum (Trading Economics, 2024).

Agriculture, forestry, and fishing are vital sectors in Nigeria, providing 40% of employment. Small farmers produce 90% of the country's agricultural output. Despite facing ongoing challenges, the oil and gas sector remains a significant component of Nigeria's economy, contributing 5.7% to real GDP in Q3 2023, accounting for 90% of goods exports by value, and providing 45% of government revenue in 2023.

The trade relationship between Nigeria and South Africa, while marked by significant challenges, holds immense potential for growth and mutual benefit (Tella, 2018; Adebajo, 2023). Addressing the issues and obstacles including import restrictions, regulatory bottlenecks, overlapping regional commitments, limited direct flights and cargo connectivity, divergent product standards, quality assurance enforcement, as well as customs and border management—that have surfaced from 2006 to 2023 requires a comprehensive and systematic approach (Taku, 2017; Adewale, 2024; Trade Policy of Nigeria, 2025). By investing in solutions to these trade-related obstacles, both countries can strengthen their economic ties and

pave the way for a more prosperous and resilient trade relationship. This paper seeks to contribute to the existing knowledge by highlighting these key issues and proposing strategies for overcoming them, thereby filling the lacuna in the current understanding of Nigeria-South Africa trade relations. The aim is to examine the nature and depth of Nigeria's trade in goods relationship with South Africa (Tella, 2018; Taku, 2017).

The trade relations between these two countries have evolved significantly since the end of apartheid in 1994 (Tella, 2018; Adebajo, 2023). As two of the largest economies in Africa, their interaction has substantial implications for the continent's economic landscape (Tella, 2018). This paper explores the progress, challenges, and prospects for boosting trade between Nigeria and South Africa during the post-apartheid era, which opened the doors for more robust international trade and bilateral relations with other countries, including Nigeria (Adebajo, 2023). Prior to this, trade interactions were limited due to political isolation and economic sanctions imposed on South Africa (Tella, 2018; Adebajo, 2023).

In the immediate post-apartheid period, Nigeria and South Africa sought to establish stronger bilateral ties. Diplomatic visits, trade missions, and the establishment of embassies in Abuja and Tshwane facilitated the initial phase of engagement. The focus was on rebuilding trust and exploring mutual economic benefits.

Political tensions have, however periodically strained their trade relations. Notable incidents include the xenophobic attacks in South Africa, which targeted Nigerian nationals and businesses, resulting in diplomatic rows between the two nations. These episodes have led to temporary disruptions in trade flows and have necessitated interventions at the highest levels of government.

Regulatory obstacles, including cumbersome bureaucratic processes and inconsistent policies, further complicate trade relations. Businesses from both countries frequently encounter difficulties in navigating the regulatory environments, leading to delays and additional costs. Harmonizing these regulations to facilitate smoother trade interactions remains a significant challenge.

Nigeria's outdated legal framework continues to present significant trade barriers (Adewale, 2024; Trade Policy of Nigeria, 2025). There are growing concerns within the export community regarding a clear contradiction between existing legislation and current government policy,

especially on export prohibitions. The specific legislation in question is the Export Prohibition Act, Cap E22, Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 2004 (originally enacted in 1989). The Act states: “The exportation from Nigeria of the goods specified in the Schedule to this Act is hereby prohibited.” The Schedule listed “yam, cassava, maize, rice, beans, and all their derivatives” among the prohibited items. This directly contradicts government initiatives to diversify exports and boost non-oil exports (Adewale, 2024; Trade Policy of Nigeria, 2025). Yam, in particular, is a major commodity being promoted for international markets including South Africa, yet its export remains technically prohibited under this law. Addressing these conflicts is critical to providing clarity, enhancing investors’ confidence, and unlocking the full potential of Nigeria’s agricultural exports (Adewale, 2024).

South Africa also terminated its Bilateral Investment Treaty (BIT) with Nigeria in 2013 as part of a border policy shift to replace BITs with domestic legislation (Protection of Investment Act, 2015). The termination created uncertainty for investors, as the new framework lacks binding international arbitration and relies on domestic resolution. Infrastructural deficiencies in both countries have hindered seamless trade interactions. Nigeria's inadequate transportation and logistics infrastructure has often resulted in delays and increased costs for South African businesses operating in the country. Similarly, South Africa's aging infrastructure and long-standing power shortages affected Nigerian investments and trade activities.

Recognizing the need to address these challenges, both Nigeria and South Africa have made concerted efforts to enhance their trade relations. Bilateral agreements, Joint Commissions, and trade facilitation initiatives have been established to foster a more conducive environment for economic exchanges.

In 2000, Nigeria and South Africa signed a Bilateral Trade Agreements (BTA) aimed at facilitating and developing trade relations based on equity and mutual benefit. By providing a framework for cooperation, they seek to mitigate the impact of political and economic challenges on trade relations.

A Joint Commission such as the Nigeria–South Africa Bi-National Commission (BNC), was established in 1999 to facilitate dialogue and collaboration between both countries (Tella, 2018; Adebajo, 2023). This Commission serves as a platform for addressing trade, investment, defence and security, science and technology, education and culture, sharing best practices, and

exploring new opportunities for economic engagement and facilitated cooperation. The Commission plays a crucial role in building the trade and broader economic relations between the two countries and fostering mutual understanding (Tella, 2018; Adebajo, 2023).

Trade facilitation initiatives, such as improved customs procedures, streamlined regulatory processes, and enhanced infrastructure development, have been implemented to support smoother trade interactions. These initiatives aim to reduce barriers to trade, lower transaction costs, and create a more favourable business environment (Safaeimanesh & Jenkins, 2021; Trade Policy of Nigeria, 2025). It is pertinent to add that evaluating the roles and impact of trade agreements on trade volumes, tariffs, and Non-Tariff Barriers (NTBs) is essential (Taku, 2017; Adewale, 2024). Additionally, existing literature often focuses on tariff reductions, but there is limited analysis on how NTBs such as customs procedures, export restrictions, import quotas, and regulatory standards affect bilateral trade flows between Nigeria and South Africa (Tella, 2018; Taku, 2017; Adewale, 2024).

Conceptual Clarifications

Some concept relevant in this paper including:

International Trade Relations: International trade, as defined by Paul Krugman and Maurice Obstfeld in *International Economics: Theory and Policy*, refers to the exchange of goods, services and capital across international borders, where specialisation and comparative advantage are basically important. Trade is recognised as an enabler for boosting economic efficiency. The comparative and competitive advantages of Nigeria and South Africa, as reflected in their economic structures, are quite different. Nigeria is predominantly a oil economy, while South Africa has a diversified economic structure (noting that it has in recent decades experience premature deindustrialisation). Both countries are strong supporters of Africa's regional integration agenda, both at sub-regional levels (SACU, SADC for South Africa, and ECOWAS for Nigeria), and at continental level in the AfCFTA.

Non-Tariff Barriers (NTBs): Non-Tariff Barriers (NTBs) are a broad and often complex category of measures that countries use to control the amount of trade across their borders beyond traditional tariffs. Non-Tariff Barriers refer to any policy, regulation, or procedure other than tariffs that countries employ to restrict imports and exports. These barriers can take various

forms, from quotas and embargoes to complex regulatory standards and administrative procedures. Unlike tariffs, which are straightforward taxes on imports, NTBs can be more subtle and multifaceted, often making them harder to quantify and address, thus affecting the ease of doing business.

Trade Facilitation: Trade facilitation is a critical aspect of international trade that aims to streamline processes, reduce barriers, and enhance the efficiency of trading activities. The **World Trade Organization (WTO)** defines trade facilitation as “the simplification and harmonization of international trade procedures, including the activities, practices, and formalities involved in collecting, presenting, communicating and processing the data required for the movement of goods in international trade.” Apparently, the agreement encompasses a range of measures designed to reduce trade costs, expedite the movement of goods, and improve the overall trading environment. The agreement according to experts is often viewed not merely as a technical customs reform but as an instrument of trade policy and economic development. Some scholars highlights that trade facilitation covers both “hard” infrastructure (ports, customs technology, transport networks) and “soft” infrastructure (rules, regulations, and institutional quality). These dimensions collectively reduce delays, uncertainty, and costs in international trade (WTO, 2024).

Nigeria - South Africa Trade: An Overview

From 2006 to 2023, Nigeria consistently exported more to South Africa than it imported, maintaining a sustained trade surplus, mainly attributed to large exports of crude oil, which have consistently accounted for approximately 99% of South Africa’s imports from Nigeria (Taku, 2017). For instance, in 2016, South Africa exported goods worth just above US\$438 million compared to over US\$2 billion in imports from Nigeria (Taku, 2017). More broadly, in 2023, Nigeria’s exports were dominated by crude petroleum (US\$43.5 billion) and petroleum gas (US\$8.38 billion), which together accounted for over 85% of total exports (Trading Economic, 2024). South Africa represented 3.8% of Nigeria’s total exports that year (WTO, 2024).

However, despite enjoying a trade surplus, the trade relationship between South Africa and Nigeria is that of a developed country (South Africa) and a developing country (Nigeria) trade relationship (Tella, 2018; Adebajo, 2023).

Exports from Nigeria to South Africa

South Africa is Nigeria's top import destination, accounting for a third (33%) of Nigeria's intra-Africa imports. Imports from South Africa include agricultural and value-added manufactured goods.

Figure 1 below illustrates Nigeria's top exported value products to South Africa. Mineral fuels, Man- Made Staple fabrics, and nuclear reactors, machinery and mechanical appliances.

Figure 1: Exports from Nigeria to South Africa

Source: International Trade Centre (ITC Trademap)

Based on UN Comtrade (UNdata) and WITS (World Bank) mineral fuels and oils remains Nigeria's dominant export to South Africa in the year 2006 accounting for US\$1.065 billion, followed by Man-made staple fabrics valued at \$25,000 and nuclear reactors, Machinery and mechanical appliances (NBS, 2024). However, a decade later, Nigeria's export basket became much more significant with an increase in exports of prepared feathers, miscellaneous manufactured products, rubber and coffee and tea.

Figure. 2

Source: International Trade Centre (ITC Trademap)

In 2016, as indicated in figure 2 above, export to South Africa from Nigeria is heavily dominated by mineral fuels, which reflects the structural nature of both economies trade relations. Evidently, it could be seen that total exports to South Africa from Nigeria across the listed product categories stands at approximately \$1.9 billion, with mineral fuels alone accounting for over 99% of this value. This underscores even at Regional trade with South Africa, crude oil and petroleum products dominates Nigeria's exports. Over reliance on mineral fuels by Nigeria for export's earnings from South Africa exposes the country to global oil prices fluctuations. Sectors such as agriculture, manufacturing, and value-add processing are seriously underrepresented. Hence, the need for expansion of the non-oil sectors, especially, processed agricultural products including light manufacturing and services could help rebalance trade relations and strengthen trade resilience.

Figure. 3

Source: International Trade Centre (ITC Trademap)

From figure 3 above, in 2023, mineral fuels were the leading export sector at US\$2.15 billion, followed by fertilizers and rubber at US\$32 million and US\$2.8 million, respectively. Other top export sectors include coffee and tea, fruits and nuts, copper, aluminium, cosmetics, machinery, beverages, electrical equipment, plastics, oil seeds and prepared feathers, amongst others. It is important to note, however, that the Nigerian market itself is huge and has limited capacity beyond mineral fuels, to the extent that any existing capacity is absorbed by the domestic market or exported to neighbouring West African countries where Nigeria enjoys preferential treatment. There is significant potential for export diversification in manufactured goods, agricultural produce, and value-added industrial products. In this regard, without concerted efforts to boost production and trade in non-oil products, there is limited scope in the short to medium term for Nigeria to consider South Africa as a market of choice for its goods and services.

South Africa’s Exports to Nigeria

Figure. 1 below illustrates the top imports sectors from South Africa between 2006 and 2023. Plastics, vehicles, machinery, and electrical equipment are the top import sectors from South Africa in terms of total values during the period under review. In 2006, iron and steel were the leading import sectors from South Africa, at US\$55 million, followed by electrical equipment and paper, at US\$51 million and US\$47 million, respectively. However, plastics replaced iron and steel as the leading import sector in 2016, followed by ships, boats, and electrical equipment.

Figure.4

Source: International Trade Centre (ITC Trademap)

As indicated in figure. 4 below, in 2023, plastics was the leading import sector, with US\$79 million, followed by fruits and nuts and prepared fruits and vegetables, with US\$78 million and US\$36 million, respectively. Other top import sectors include aircraft, chemicals, miscellaneous edible preparations, cereals, miscellaneous articles of base metal, paper, residues and waste from food industries, and cosmetics. There are huge opportunities for South Africa

to expand into the processed food, machinery, and transport equipment exports. And for Nigeria, heavy dependency on imports of essential consumer goods and capital pose high risk.

Figure. 5

Source: ITC Trade map November 2024

Factors Influencing Trade Relations between Nigeria and South Africa

Domestic production is essential in determining the nature of trade between South Africa and Nigeria. The ability of both countries to produce goods and services affects their trade balance, dependence on imports, and capacity to export to one another. Nigeria, as Africa’s largest economy, relies heavily on crude oil exports, while South Africa has a diversified economy with strong manufacturing, mining, and service sectors. According to data from the International Trade Centre (ITC), in 2023, Nigeria's top exports to South Africa included crude oil, petroleum products, liquefied natural gas, and agricultural commodities. South Africa exported manufactured goods, machinery, and processed food products.

In 2023, South Africa imported approximately \$2.15 billion in Nigerian crude oil, while Nigeria imported South African manufactured goods worth \$424million.

Nigeria's dependence on crude oil, which constitutes over 90% of its export revenue, reflects a very high level of export concentration (Trading Economic, 2024; WTO, 2024). Conversely, South Africa's diversified manufacturing sector gives it an advantage in exporting a wide range of finished goods, including automobiles, pharmaceuticals, and industrial machinery (Tella, 2018; Adebajo, 2023). Trade relations between the two countries are further determined by fluctuations in global oil prices and South Africa's ability to produce competitive manufactured goods (Tella, 2018). The African Continental Free Trade Area (AfCFTA) is expected to increase trade between Nigeria and South Africa by reducing trade barriers, enhancing market access, and fostering industrial collaboration (Anoje & Akinkugbe, 2021). According to the United Nations Economic Commission for Africa (UNECA), intra-African trade could grow by 52.3% under AfCFTA, benefiting both economies by expanding the scope of trade beyond traditional goods (Anoje & Akinkugbe, 2021).

Trade relations between Nigeria and South Africa are heavily impacted by the dynamics of labour markets and employment levels. For instance, South Africa's informal sector accounts for 17% of its labour force, significantly lower than Nigeria at 68% and Africa's average of 58%. This disparity matters because South Africa's formal sector is capital-intensive and unable to absorb its high unemployment levels, leaving the small informal economy insufficient to fill the gap. In contrast, Nigeria's large informal sector acts as a cushion, absorbing workers who cannot find formal employment. The availability of skilled and unskilled labour, wage differentials, and labour market policies influence bilateral trade. South Africa has a more structured labour market with strong trade unions and a higher proportion of skilled workers compared to Nigeria (though it also faces skills deficits). Nigeria, conversely, has a large informal labour sector, with over 60% of its workforce employed in informal jobs, according to the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS, 2024). This affects labour productivity and the ability of Nigerian industries to compete with South African manufacturers. A shift in trade could significantly impact industries in the formal sectors in either country; however, the capacity of each economy to absorb disruptions differs dramatically. South Africa's limited

informal buffer could result in job losses, thus triggering trade pressures which could worsen unemployment more severely than in Nigeria.

Unemployment rates in both Nigeria and South Africa have direct effects (reduction in household purchasing power) and indirect effects (influence on trade policy choices) on their trade relations. In 2023, Nigeria recorded an unemployment rate of 33.3%, while South Africa's unemployment rate stood at 32.9% (Statista). High unemployment in both countries presents challenges for economic growth, as consumer purchasing power remains weak. However, South African businesses have increasingly invested in Nigeria's telecommunications, banking, and retail sectors, creating jobs and enhancing trade ties. South African companies such as MTN, Shoprite, and Standard Bank have expanded operations in Nigeria, employing thousands of Nigerians and contributing to the country's service industry (Tella, 2018; Adebajo, 2023). Equally, Nigerian companies like Dangote Group have explored investment opportunities in South Africa, particularly in the cement and food processing industries. In April 2008, the Dangote Group acquired a 45% stake in Sephaku Cement, a subsidiary of Sephaku Holdings, for approximately R3 billion (ZAR) through a private placement. However, by 2010, the Dangote Group made additional investments, increasing its stake to 64% and consolidating control over Sephaku Cement (Tella, 2018; Adebajo, 2023).

In 2021, Access Bank Group of Nigeria acquired Grobank Limited (formerly Bank of Athens South Africa) for approximately US\$60 million. The bank was rebranded as Access Bank South Africa and launched retail banking operations in June that same year.

Both countries' technological advancement and industrial capacity significantly affect trade dynamics. South Africa has a more advanced industrial base, with cutting-edge technology in manufacturing, mining, and automotive industries. In contrast, Nigeria's industrial sector is underdeveloped, with limited technological capabilities and reliance on imported machinery (Tella, 2018; Adebajo, 2023). South Africa's key industries, such as automobile manufacturing (BMW, Volkswagen, and Toyota assembly plants), pharmaceutical production, and mining technology, provide it with a competitive edge in trade. Nigerian firms rely on South African industrial equipment and technology for production (Tella, 2018; Adebajo, 2023). The adoption of digital technology also influences trade. South Africa has a more developed digital economy, with high internet penetration and a strong e-commerce sector. Nigerian start-ups in fintech,

such as Flutterwave and Paystack, have collaborated with South African financial institutions, enhancing trade in digital services. According to the Nigeria Startup Act (2022), which provides a legal framework to support hubs, startups, and innovation ecosystems with tax incentives and funding opportunities. According to TechParley, citing the Global Startup Ecosystem Report, Nigeria hosts more than 90 active tech hubs, with Lagos alone housing about half of them, placing Nigeria as the continent's most vibrant tech ecosystem.

The role of trade agreements in Nigeria-South Africa trade relations cannot be overemphasised. In 2000, Nigeria and South Africa signed a Bilateral Investment Treaty titled the "Agreement between the Government of the Republic of South Africa and the Federal Republic of Nigeria for the Reciprocal Promotion and Protection of Investments." The treaty aims to create favourable conditions for investment by investors of either country in the territory of the other, promoting and protecting investments to stimulate business initiatives and contribute to development and prosperity for both nations (Tella, 2018; Adebajo, 2023). Additionally, both countries are members of international organisations such as the World Trade Organisation (WTO), International Monetary Fund (IMF), and African Union Commission (AUC), fostering trade policies that promote economic collaboration (WTO, 2024; Okoro, 2013). Nigeria's initial reluctance to sign the AfCFTA agreement in 2018 created tensions in trade relations. However, after signing the agreement in 2019, trade between the two countries improved, with projections indicating a potential increase in trade volume by over 30% by 2030 (Anoje & Akinkugbe, 2021).

According to the Nigeria-South Africa Chamber of Commerce, citing the 2022 Coface economic report, trade between the two nations reached \$3.2 billion in 2022, with South African firms increasing investments in Nigeria's financial and telecommunications sectors (NSACC, 2025). In October 1999, the South Africa-Nigeria Bi-National Commission (BNC) was established by the South African and Nigerian governments (Tella, 2018; Adebajo, 2023). The Bi-National Commission was established to consolidate and strengthen bilateral political, economic, and trade relations between Nigeria and South Africa. It has a mandate to review cooperation between the two countries on foreign affairs, public enterprises and infrastructure, agriculture, minerals and energy, trade, industry and finance, among others. The cooperation of both countries through the South Africa-Nigeria Bi-National Commission seeks to create a

climate conducive for the creation of a better quality of life for all. The Commission is also seen as a platform in which both countries can jointly, as partners, impact positively, in conjunction with other African countries, on regional peace and security, socio-economic development, poverty alleviation, and the prevention of crime and corruption (Tella, 2018; Adebajo, 2023).

The consumer market size significantly impacts trade relations between Nigeria and South Africa. Nigeria, with a population of over 220 million, represents Africa's largest consumer market (World Population Review, 2024), while South Africa, with a population of 62.3 million, has a higher per capita income and consumer spending power. Nigeria's growing middle class has encouraged demand for South African consumer goods, electronics, and retail products (Tella, 2018; Adebajo, 2023). Shoprite's expansion in Nigeria until 2021 was a testament to South Africa's retail sector tapping into Nigeria's vast consumer base. However, due to economic challenges and regulatory hurdles, Shoprite exited Nigeria, indicating the difficulties of doing business in the country (Tella, 2018; Adebajo, 2023).

Equally, Nigerian companies exporting agricultural products, such as cocoa, sesame seeds, and cashew nuts, have found a lucrative market in South Africa (Taku, 2017; Tella, 2018). The increasing demand for organic and agricultural products in South Africa presents an opportunity for Nigerian exporters to diversify their trade beyond crude oil (Adewale, 2024; Tella, 2018; Trade Policy of Nigeria, 2025).

Infrastructure plays a vital role in facilitating trade between Nigeria and South Africa. Efficient transport networks, ports, and logistics systems determine the cost and ease of trade. South Africa, although with some challenges, has a well-developed infrastructure, with modern ports, rail networks, and highways that facilitate the movement of goods. In contrast, Nigeria faces significant infrastructure deficits, with poor road networks, congested ports, and unreliable power supply hindering trade (Adewale, 2024; Trade Policy of Nigeria, 2025). The inefficiencies at Nigerian ports, such as the Apapa Port, increase the cost of imports and exports, making trade less competitive (Trade Policy of Nigeria, 2025; Adewale, 2024). The Lagos-Johannesburg trade route plays a key role in trade volume, with airlines like South African Airways and Air Peace operating frequent and direct flights carrying high-value and

perishable goods. However, trade costs remain high due to tariffs, regulatory bottlenecks, and logistics challenges (Safaeimanesh & Jenkins, 2021; Taku, 2017).

Finally, trade relations between Nigeria and South Africa are shaped by multiple factors, including domestic production capacity, employment levels, technological advancement, trade agreements, consumer demand, and infrastructure. While both countries have significant trade potential, challenges such as trade imbalances, regulatory barriers, and infrastructure deficits hinder optimal trade expansion. The AfCFTA presents a unique opportunity to deepen trade ties for both countries by removing trade barriers and fostering industrial collaboration.

Challenges for Nigeria and South Africa

Despite the potential advantages of strong trade relations, Nigeria and South Africa face several barriers that impede the two countries from fully achieving economic cooperation. These difficulties are complex and multidimensional, involving financial, regulatory, infrastructure, and economic hurdles that require organised efforts (Tella, 2018; Adebajo, 2023). The problem of trade imbalances is one of the main obstacles to the two nations' economic cooperation. South Africa is concerned about the sustainability of this pattern because the trade balance has continuously heavily favoured Nigeria (Taku, 2017; Tella, 2018). The imbalance frequently indicates an uneven flow of goods and services, which reduces South Africa's gains from the trade relationship and jeopardises the partnership's long-term viability (Tella, 2018; Adebajo, 2023). Another main challenge is the inadequate infrastructure in both nations, particularly Nigeria. Poor infrastructure severely limits the efficient movement of goods and services between the two countries. Transportation networks, power supply, and logistics systems are underdeveloped, leading to high transaction costs and increased barriers to trade (Adewale, 2024; Trade Policy of Nigeria 2025; Safaeimanesh & Jenkins, 2021). This situation hampers the flow of goods and weakens the potential for businesses to expand their operations across borders, stifling economic growth (Tella, 2018; Adebajo, 2023).

In addition to infrastructural deficits, differing regulations, trade policies, and administrative procedures hinder bilateral trade. Both countries have their own set of rules and standards, which complicate trade and business operations. Regulatory barriers create delays, increase costs, and make it difficult to conduct trade across borders.

Currency fluctuations are another critical factor threatening South Africa's and Nigeria's trade stability. Businesses involved in cross-border transactions experience uncertainty due to the fluctuations in the exchange rates between the South African Rand and the Nigerian Naira. This volatility makes trade agreements less profitable, particularly for businesses with significant import and export volumes. Long-term financial planning is made more difficult by the volatility of currency values, making it more difficult for companies to guarantee steady, predictable trade profits. For instance, MTN's \$1.7 billion fine in 2018 highlighted regulatory unpredictability under Nigeria's Communication Act (2003), which lacks clarity.

Significant obstacles to the expansion of trade between the two nations are protectionist policies, such as tariffs and non-tariff barriers. Both countries have occasionally taken such actions to protect their industries. These regulations have the unintended consequence of restricting trade and keeping foreign companies out of essential industries, even though their stated goal may be safeguarding local markets (Adewale, 2024; Trade Policy of Nigeria, 2025). These protectionist policies reduce the advantages of bilateral trade agreements and slow economic cooperation (Tella, 2018; Adebajo, 2023). The trade facilitation process is increasingly challenging. The movement of goods can be slowed down by customs procedures, which are frequently tedious and ineffective, especially within regional value chains (Safaeimanesh & Jenkins, 2021). Quotas, licenses, and product standards are non-tariff barriers that impede trade and make it more challenging for companies to transport goods across international borders freely (Adewale, 2024; Taku, 2017). The ensuing administrative roadblocks and delays raise business costs and reduce the two nations' ability to work together (Safaeimanesh & Jenkins, 2021; Trade Policy of Nigeria, 2025).

Additionally, a massive problem in both countries is limited access to financing, especially for small and medium-sized businesses (SMEs). These companies frequently have trouble raising the money needed to improve operations, make technological investments, or enter new markets (Adewale, 2024; Trade Policy of Nigeria, 2025). Without sufficient funding, SMEs cannot take full advantage of the opportunities that trade relations present, which slows the growth of both national economies and makes it more difficult for them to integrate into regional and global value chains (Tella, 2018; Adebajo, 2023; Safaeimanesh & Jenkins, 2021).

Conclusion

This study has examined Nigeria-South Africa trade and broader economic relationship. There are a lot of growth prospects in Nigeria's trade relationship with South Africa; however, to maximize the potential of the bilateral trading opportunities, both countries should re-establish a common strategic approach if the continent's voice is to carry weight on the global stage. In this regard, both governments must be deliberate in developing targeted policies aimed at resolving trade-related barriers, including infrastructure, Non-Tariff Barriers (NTBs), standards/conformity assessment and simplified customs procedures for a sustainable economic transformation. To reduce trade costs and promote more seamless exchanges, a concentrated effort to invest in infrastructure such as energy, transportation, and logistics networks is essential to this transition. Managing as well as eliminating non-tariff barriers, harmonization and standardizing regulations framework, and simplifying trade processes will guarantee the smooth flow of goods within local value chains. The need for implementation of the 10th and 11th Decisions of the BNC between Nigeria and South Africa cannot be over emphasized, including the accelerations of the AfCFTA.

Investments in education and skill development are essential to raise workforce productivity and boost participation in industries with strong growth potential. Expanding access to financing will further support their integration into these value chains, particularly for small and medium-sized businesses. Long-term success requires industrial policies that promote value addition and competitiveness within regional chains. Additionally, encouraging investment flows and quickening the growth of Africa's regional value chains will require stronger regional cooperation. Furthermore, Nigeria must review its import bans, especially on products of interest to South Africa. By tackling these challenges, both countries could significantly increase their competitiveness within and outside the continent, diversify its economy, and generate job opportunities.

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